

UPBRINGING-AS A FACTOR IN ENSURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHILD

Khakimova N.B.

Gulistan State University lecturer

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Abstract. *This article includes extensive information on the sequence, content, and importance of factors that ensure the development of a child's personality, the results of psychological research, and well-founded opinions of foreign and Eastern scholars on this topic.*

Keywords: *child, environment, family, society, education, value, factor, religion, positive, negative.*

The development of the child's personality is most effective in communicating with peers and adults in various activities. Upbringing, heredity (pedigree) and the environment occupy a fundamental place in the development of the child. If these three factors positively affect the child, he can become a competent person in the future and become an infantile person if he is affected from the negative side. Sufficient feedback and opinions have been expressed in the works of Islam and Ulama on the factors affecting the formation of the child. At the same time, Western philosophers also described their views on the development of the child. Below we will cite the opinions of the Western and Islamic world about the factors that influence the formation of the child. Thoughts of Western philosophers about the formation of a child.

Biological orientation – proponents of this orientation know that natural-biological (hereditary) factors play a decisive role in the development of a human child as a person. They believe that only innate traits passed down from Offspring-ancestors develop during the mother's womb. They limit the role of upbringing and environment. Supporters of the direction are Aristotle, Plato. The direction of preformism-according to the manifestations of this current, which arose in the philosophy of the XVI century, all the features belonging to the future person will be acquired as soon as the child is in the mother's womb. They completely denied the role of upbringing and environment. In the formation of Man, the influence of upbringing, heredity and environment for the formation of a child is especially emphasized in the works of Islam and thinkers. Within these three factors, the role of upbringing is considered particularly significant. But the strength and result of the influence of upbringing is determined by the cooperation of factors such as heredity and environment. Because if there is a deficiency in offspring and environment, the influence of upbringing may not be felt. Below we bring the views of Islam and Ulama about the three factors.

Upbringing is the external and most important factor affecting human maturity. "Discipline" is an Arabic word meaning that he raised, led, reformed. Rogib Asfihani of the Islamic Ulama defines upbringing as: "upbringing is the act of moving one thing from one state to another and bringing it to the point of completion. One of the meanings of upbringing is to cultivate the Religious, Thought and moral powers of a person with harmony and balance". The messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) emphasizes the incompetence of the role of parents in bringing upbringing to man. It is narrated from Abu Hurayra (roziyallohu anhu): "Prophet (peace be upon him and sallam): "every child born is born only with fitrat (pure nature). So his parents make him Jewish or Christian or genial...". We will learn from this hadith Sharif

that the opinions of Western philosophers and currents that promote the idea that heredity, that is, the biological factor, plays a fundamental role in the formation of Man, are unfounded and the importance of upbringing.

The leading place in the social development of the child lies in the assimilation of the moral values of his people and, later, knowledge and acquisition of universal moral values. Closely related to social progress is the moral education of preschool children. The experience of moral behavior of preschool children is formed in the process of communication with adults and is strengthened in various joint activities and relationships with peers. Children develop concepts such as learning, creativity, social orientation, a healthy lifestyle is brought up, and they begin to understand how to behave in a social environment.

Of the middle Asian thinkers, Farabi and Abu Ali ibn Sina have noted the importance of factors affecting human education. Forobius emphasized the importance of education in human maturation: to become a decent person, a person has two different opportunities: education and upbringing. Through education, theoretical maturation is achieved, and upbringing is the path that leads to the creation of moral dignity and practical activities in communication with people..."he says. Abu Ali ibn Sina specifically mentioned the role of parents in raising a family: "when a child is born, first of all, the father should give him a good name, and then bring him up well... If good methods of upbringing are used in the family, the family will be happy."

In the development of a child's personality, the influence of offspring is understood as the physical characteristics that are inherited from parent to child (the structure of the body, hair, eye, skin color, stature), as well as the movement of the body in a vertical position, the development of thinking and speech, the ability to work, the abilities and characteristics that pass in Islam, special attention is paid to lineage. Because when the offspring is pure and the parents are enlightened, moral, these characteristics pass to the child in an innate state and become a perfect person in the future. If a parent is far from enlightenment and immoral, the child born of them can harm society. But the abilities and traits that pass from the parents in an innate state cannot develop in their own way, as if it were in a "mudder" State, for its awakening-development, a favorable environment and constant upbringing are needed. One of the factors affecting the maturation of the child is the external environment. The environment is understood as a set of external events that naturally affect a person. This includes the natural environment, the family environment and the social environment. Natural (geographical) environment – affects the way of life, character and labor activity of a person.

For example, a person living in the North is distinguished from a person living in the south not only by his physical appearance, but also by his psyche, worldview and features.

Family environment-important in the formation of a person. Because the child sees his parents, relatives, with an eye. The period of its physical and mental development is formed under the influence of the family. If the family has an Islamic environment, the child's morality will grow up beautiful and virtuous. The social environment-production relations and the social laws that regulate them-have a special effect on a person. As a result of social interaction, that is, interpersonal interaction, a person's child is prepared for life and work, acquires the necessary experience and knowledge. In society, the spiritual environment is good, justice is a priority, it has a positive effect on human activity, and vice versa, it has a negative effect.

The family is the most important link in the social environment that surrounds the child. His influence on the formation of a child's personality is benihoya senior. The child's independence is relative, and he will need adult care and support from the crowd. Father-Oria's thought and

attitude will have such great motivating power during this period that it will serve as a regulator of behavior and a stimulator of psychic development. Psychiatrists note that raising a child with excessive severity is one of the factors that cause neuroses and psychosthenia in him. Of course, the relationship in each family is unique and unrepeatable. However, there is also a common aspect of the parent-child relationship. Relationships in the middle are often categorized as "Democratic" and "authoritarian", depending on what methods parents use in managing children's behavior.

For a "democratic" form of family influence on children, the following are typical: the child is allowed a lot, communicates a lot with the child, treats him with confidence and respect, parents try not to impose prohibitions, to the death of which they seek to explain to children the rule of order in the family, try to answer as much as possible. The "authoritarian" environment in the family is characterized by an excess of excessive prohibitions on children. "Dominant" parents demand complete submission from the child. In such a family, communication is held, which is aimed at explaining the rules of behavior to children. It is determined that there will be a certain difference in the personal characteristics of my child, raised in "authoritarian" and "Democratic" families. Children of a "Democratic" family tend to be creative, proactive, pro-leadership, deny conformism (subordination of Group Thought), feel more emotive in their social relationships.

From sociometric experiments, it turns out that the environment in the family is warm, while the relationship between parent and child is built on a democratic basis, the child acquires a high position in the team among his peers, and, on the contrary, children brought up in an unhealthy family take a much lower position. It has been found that the more pampered a child is, the slower he is made as a person, he is prone to passivity and apathy, perhaps later his character is formed as weak. The psychological climate in the family, that is, the character of communication with children, affection, attentive attitude, plays an extremely important role in the formation of a growing human moral image. Therefore, competent human Education First assumes that the environment in the family is healthy.

Education, environment, and heredity are therefore important to human maturation. Why don't we meet people like Imam Bukhari, Farabi, Beruniy and Ghazzali, who lived in the past today? Because their heredity was pure, their parents were righteous and righteous, during the period in which they lived, science, enlightenment and progress reached their peak, that is, their parents and teachers, whose environment was good and, most importantly, in charge of the upbringing of our ancestors, performed their duties excellently, without defects in their upbringing.

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